

ISSIQLIK TARQALISH TENGLAMASI UCHUN KOSHI MASALASI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada issiqlik tenglamasiga qo'yilgan to'g'ri va teskari masalalarning umumlashgan yechimlarining to'g'riligi o'rganilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: *Uzluksizlik, funksional qator, Fure koeffitsienti, tor tebranish tenglamasi.*

ANNOTATION

The dissertation “Non local boundary conditional direct and inverse problems in an unbounded domain for the heat propagation in three-dimensional space” is one of the important sections of mathematics. Interest in this field is determined by the theoretical significance of the obtained results and their practical applications.

Kirish

Matematik fizikaning juda ko'p masalalarini xususiy hosilali tenglamalar ko'rinishida tavsiflash mumkin. Bunday tavsivlashda unga mos bo'lgan chegaraviy masalalar yechimini tabiiy aniqlash imkoniyati mavjud va shu bilan birga, ularni yechishga ma'lum usullarni qo'llash mumkin. Tabiatda uchraydigan jarayonlarni kasr tartibli tenglamalar aniqroq ifoda etadi.

Issiqlik tarqalish tenglamasi.

Koshi masalasi: Tekislikdagi $\Omega = \{(x, t) : 0 < x < l, 0 < t < T\}$ sohada bir jinsli

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = a^2 \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} \quad (a = \text{const}) \quad (1)$$

issiqlik tarqalish tenglamasining

$$u(x,0) = \varphi(x), \quad 0 \leq x \leq l \quad (2)$$

boshlang'ich va

$$u(0,t) = 0, \quad u(l,t) = 0, \quad 0 \leq t < T \quad (3)$$

bir jinsli chegaraviy shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi regulyar yechimi topilsin.

Ta'rif: (1) tenglamaning regulyar yoki klassik yechimi deb Ω sohada, tenglamada qatnashuvchi o'zining hosilalari bilan uzluksiz va tenglamani ayniyatga aylantiruvchi $u=u(x,y)$ funksiyaga aytiladi.

Aralash masalani o'zgaruvchilarni ajratish (yoki Furiye) usuli bilan yechamiz.

Bu usulga asosan (1) tenglamaning yechimini

$$u(x,t) = X(x)T(t) \quad (4)$$

shaklda izlasak, quyidagi

$$X''(x) + \lambda X(x) = 0, \quad (5)$$

$$T'(x) + a^2 \lambda T(t) = 0 \quad (6)$$

ikkita oddiy differensial tenglama hosil bo'ladi, bunda $\lambda = \text{const}$. (4) ifoda va (3) chegaraviy shartlardan (5) tenglama uchun quyidagi

$$X(0) = X(l) = 0 \quad (7)$$

chegaraviy shartlar kelib chiqadi.

(5), (7) masala - xos son va xos funksiyalarni topish xaqidagi Shturm-Liuuill masalasi bo'lib, u tor tebranish tenglamasi uchun aralash masalani yechishda ham qurilgan edi.

Bu masalaning xos sonlari $\lambda_n = \left(\frac{\pi n}{l}\right)^2$, $(n=1,2,\dots)$, bu xos sonlarga mos

trivial bo'lmagan xos funksiyalari $X_n(x) = \sin \frac{\pi n}{l} x$ ko'rinishda ekanligini

aniqlagan edik. $\lambda = \lambda_n$ bo'lganda (6) tenglamaning umumiy yechimi

$$T_n(t) = a_n e^{-(a\pi n/l)^2 t}$$

ko‘rinishga ega bo‘lib, (1.2.4) tenglikka asosan

$$U_n(x,t) = X_n(x)T_n(t) = a_n e^{-\left(\frac{\pi na}{l}\right)^2 t} \sin \frac{\pi n}{l} x$$

funksiyalar (a_n -ixtiyoriy, o‘zgarmas sonlar) (1) tenglamani va (3) chegaraviy shartni qanoatlantiradi. Tenglama bir jinsli bo‘lgani uchun bu yechimlar yig‘indisi yana yechim bo‘ladi. Shuning uchun (1) tenglamaning (2), (3) shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi yechimini

$$u(x,t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n e^{-\left(\frac{\pi na}{l}\right)^2 t} \sin \frac{\pi n}{l} x \quad (8)$$

qator ko‘rinishida izlaymiz. Agar (8) Funksional qator va uning t bo‘yicha birinchi, x bo‘yicha ikkinchi tartibli hosilalari tekis yaqinlashuvchi bo‘lsa, u holda bum qator yig‘indisi (1) tenglamani va (3) chegaraviy shartlarni qanoatlantiradi. Boshlang‘ich shartni ham qanoatlantirishini talab qilsak,

$$u(x,0) = \varphi(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n \sin \frac{\pi n}{l} x$$

tenglikka ega bo‘lamiz. Bu tenglikni $\varphi(x)$ funksiyaning $(0,l)$ oraliqdagi sinuslar bo‘yicha Fure qatoriga yoyilmasi desak, u holda a_n Fure koeffitsienti bo‘lib,

$$a_n = \frac{2}{l} \int_0^l \varphi(x) \sin \frac{\pi n}{l} x dx \quad (9)$$

formula bo‘yicha topiladi.

(9) tenglikka asosan (1)-(3) masalaning (8) yechimini quyidagi ko‘rinishda yozish mumkin

$$u(x,t) = \int_0^l G(x,y,t) \varphi(y) dy, \quad (10)$$

bu yerda

$$G(x, y, t) = \frac{2}{l} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\left(\frac{\pi n a}{l}\right)^2 t} \sin \frac{\pi n}{l} x \sin \frac{\pi n}{l} y.$$

Bu funksiya oniy manbaning ta'sir funksiyasi deyiladi.

1- Teorema. Agar $[0, l]$ kesmada $\varphi(x)$ funksiya

1. uzluksiz;
2. bo'lakli-uzluksiz hosilaga ega va
3. $\varphi(0)=\varphi(l)=0$

shartni qanoatlantirsa, u holda (8) qator aralash masalaning $\bar{\Omega}$ da uzluksiz va cheksiz differentsiallanuvchi yechimi bo'ladi.

(2) funksiya aralash masalaning yechimi bo'lishi uchun, (2) boshlang'ich shartda berilgan $\varphi(x)$ funksiya uzluksiz, bo'lakli silliq va boshlang'ich hamda chegaraviy shartlarning moslashganlik shartiga ($\varphi(0)=\varphi(l)=0$) bo'ysunishi kerak. Lekin $\varphi(x)$ funksiyaning uzluksizligi va moslashganlik shartini qanoatlantirishi amaliyot uchun og'ir shartdir.

Masalan, $U_0 = const$ temperaturagacha isitilgan va chetlarida nol temperaturaga ega bo'lgan, soviyotgan sterjenda issiqlik tarqalish masalasida, boshlang'ich va chegaraviy shartlarning moslashganlik sharti bajarilmaydi, ya'ni $\varphi(0)=\varphi(l)=0=U_0 \neq 0$. Bu holda quyidagi teorema o'rinalidir.

2- Teorema. Agar $[0, l]$ kesmada $\varphi(x)$ funksiya bo'lakli-uzluksiz (I - tur uzilishlarga ega) bo'lsa, u holda (10) funksiya:

- 1) Ω sohada (1) tenglamasining yechimi bo'ladi;
- 2) $\bar{\Omega} = \{(x, t) : 0 \leq x \leq l, 0 \leq t \leq T\}$ sohada chegaralangan;
- 3) (3) chegaraviy shartlarni qanoatlantiradi;
- 4) $t=0$ da $\varphi(x)$ funksiyaning uzluksiz nuqtalarida uzluksiz va $u(x, 0)=\varphi(x)$

bo'ladi.

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PSYCHOLOGY OF STORIES AND NOVELS OF ULUG‘BEK HAMDAM

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses one of the most important topics of modern literature - the concept of artistic psychology and its history. As an introduction to the concept, theoretical views of literary scholars and definitions of the term by Uzbek scholars are given.

Key words: *psychology, social consciousness, life reality, modernism, realism, character, concept.*

Introduction. A work of art is a product of the artist's thinking, in which the life of man and society, his destiny and destiny find their image. In every works of art, the events that have happened or may happen in our lives are conveyed by the author to the reader based on the laws of art continues to form. The problems raised in the works of art, the issues referred to the reader's attention and judgment - the theme and content of the work of art are closely related to the social environment when the work was created. In order to deeply and completely reveal the character of the artistic image in the work, the author used the means of artistic imagery as well as the means of psychological imagery. In the work, the author goes deep into the inner world of the hero, describes the mental world of the character in detail depicts, the feelings of the soul - it is called "artistic psychology".